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Deliverable 3.3b: Report on cost efficiency and cost-benefits of selected preventive scenarios

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium, **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

Summary

Bayesian decision analysis is usually employed to make decisions in the presence of uncertainty. A common cost-benefit analysis approach, which is novel in the risk analysis of hydrologic/hydraulic applications, and a Bayesian decision analysis are applied to aid the decision making of implementing mitigation measures for groundwater resources management. The alternative option examined is a variation in terms of groundwater use only and possible over-pumping violations. The methodological steps are analytically presented and are associated with the original developed code. The results indicate that the probability of the uncertainty is the driving variable that determines the optimal decision, and depending on the unknown probability handling, the methodology may lead to a different optimal decision. Thus, the proposed tool can help the decision makers to examine and compare different scenarios using different approaches before making a decision considering the cost of a hydrologic/hydraulic project and the varied economic charges that water table limit violations can cause inside an audit interval. In contrast to practices that assess the effect of each proposed action separately considering only current knowledge of the examined issue. This tool aids decision making by considering prior information and the sampling distribution of future successful audits.

Introduction

In this report the proposed methodology, described in detail in deliverable 3.3A, is applied using institutional datasets collected from the project partners for each case study site. The results are compared to those obtained from the application of global datasets providing a framework of usefulness and potential fusion of monitoring and global data to substitute missing values.

Bayesian decision theory quantifies the yield of various decisions using probabilities and costs that accompany such decisions. Therefore, it was primarily developed to utilize additional information to reduce the risk of uncertain decisions. The basic aim is to choose the class for which the expected loss is the smallest. The problem is posed in probabilistic terms, and it is assumed that all relevant probabilities are unknown. The probabilistic approach is powerful if the probability distributions are indeed known, but this is often not the case. A common way to overcome this difficulty is to apply Bayesian decision theory by establishing a prior distribution (Berger, 1985; O'Malley and Vesselinov, 2014; Varouchakis et al., 2016).

The decision-making process, according to the Bayesian risk, is a methodology that combines the expected loss of a specific decision with the probability, θ , of the loss that will occur. The methodology is based on statistical knowledge that is produced after sampling and using prior knowledge information. The latter is known as "soft information" (Czado and Brechmann, 2014; Lerche and Paleologos, 2001; Parent and Bernier, 2003). The basic characteristics of the Bayesian decision theory are the state parameters θ_i ($i = 0 \dots n$) that correspond to the number

of stated decisions, the state of the possible decisions or actions $A(i)$, and the state of the expected loss function that corresponds to each decision, $L(A(i), \theta_i)$. The set θ that considers all the possible state parameters, θ_i , is known as the parametric space. Set A contains all possible actions $A(i)$. A loss function $L(A(i), \theta_i)$ is defined for all $A(i)$, θ_i that belong to $[\theta \times A]$.

The Bayesian decision method is applied herein to address the dilemma of whether to apply mitigation measures for irrigation and drinking water purposes or to apply a groundwater resources management policy in terms of scaled overpumping (Varouchakis et al., 2019).

This work provides a tool (Appendix) that considers, beside the Bayesian decision method, a cost-benefit analysis approach to assess the stated dilemma and to help the decision makers to compare techniques for testing potential strategies for decision dilemmas in hydrological applications.

Case studies

Four case studies were considered for the application of the proposed cost benefit analysis methodology: Malia-Crete-Greece, Arborea-Sardinia-Italy, Erdemli-Mersin-Turkey, Wadi El Bey-Tunisia. All the necessary hydrogeological data for each case study are described in detail Deliverable 2.1, while source hydrological data and management information were collected and provided from partners for each site after the completion of a relative questioner. The preferable mitigation action, in most case studies as an alternative mitigation measure to groundwater overexploitation, was the reservoir construction. Only in Malia site aquifer recharge was preferred due to the operation of a reservoir. The processing of significant information is presented in results and discussion section.

Methodology

Decision-Making Process

The decision-making process described in detail in deliverable 3.3A involves two stages: state estimation and decision making. For state estimation, firstly, all the state parameters θ_i are defined. However, in the Bayesian approach, a state parameter is an unknown quantity and is considered a random variable that must be determined. The procedure of estimating each θ_i involves previous knowledge on the examined issue and the use of the subjective prior distribution $\pi(\theta_i)$ that expresses the prior information for each state parameter. Next, the Bayesian risk function is obtained to estimate the optimal decision or the decision with the minimum expected risk (Berger, 1985; Lerche and Paleologos, 2001; Wolfson et al., 1996). The latter also applies in terms of a cost-benefit analysis procedure and denotes the preferable action. The Bayesian decision-making process follows these four steps:

1. Set up the decision-making problem by introducing the possible actions set A and the parametric space θ .
2. Establish the expected loss function for each decision $A(i)$, and provide the state of the goal function. If at this step, the parameters θ_i are considered known, then the decision process is called a cost-benefit analysis, and Step 4 is directly applied. If not, then both Steps 3 and 4 apply.
3. Develop the subjective prior distributions for each θ_i quantifying the previous information.
4. Combine Steps 1, 2, and 3 via the risk function. The decision with the minimum expected risk is the optimal decision.

Figure 1 presents a flowchart that describes the methodological steps of Bayesian and cost-benefit risk analysis.

Fig. 1 Flowchart of Bayesian Risk and cost-benefit risk analysis

Cost-benefit Analysis Approach

The Bayesian analysis assumes the probability of over-pumping as an unknown variable. Thus, to be quantified, the subjective prior distribution was used by fitting the parameters of the suitable distribution to water table level and rainfall data. The fitting process was applied using the "distribution fitter" app of Matlab software. However, when the probability is quantified, cost-benefit approach can be used as a risk analysis tool. The Bayesian risk function for each classic alternative action is then substituted by the expected risk, which is denoted by the loss function. The risk cost-benefit analysis approach combines the expected loss (or Expected Net Present Value (ENPV)) with the probability the loss will occur. The conditional inequality, $R(A(1)) > R(A(0))$, is now reformed as follows:

$$L(A(1), Y) > L(A(0), Y). \quad (1)$$

When decision $A(0)$ is optimal Eq. (1) reflects that $C - L(A(0), Y) > 0$. On the other hand, if $C - L(A(0), Y) < 0$ the best option is decision $A(1)$. The goal function, in cost-benefit analysis terms, responds to the Expected Net Loss Present Value (ENLPV). The ENLPV for both decision $A(1)$ and $A(0)$ is given by

$$ENLPV = C - L(A(0), Y). \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) is the cost-benefit model. By performing iterations for various numbers of Y , which denote the number of successful audits (over-pumping violations), a range of different values of ENLPV is provided, which can be analyzed statistically and graphically (Florio et al., 2008; Hussen, 2012).

On the other hand, the ENLPV function in terms of potential drought years is formed as follows:

$$ENLPV = C + AC + MY_1 - L(A(0), Y). \quad (3)$$

By applying the cost-benefit analysis approach in terms of variable Y_1 values also (potential dry periods), a new empirical cumulative distribution function plot of the ENLPV will be obtained. Then the optimal decision is provided according to the interpretation of Eq. 2.

Results and Discussion

Herein, the previously stated risk analysis methodologies are applied and compared under the same terms and their results are discussed. The penalty fine values and loss function were formed in order the stakeholders and the local managing authorities to develop environmental behavior and to acquire long-term environmental policy. The penalty values were formed in order their scaled variability based on the potential improper aquifer management to be comparative to the cost of the preferred mitigation measure, which is a long-term solution. The penalty values were based and inspired on similar fines applied by different water resources management authorities in the United States. In the European Union, each member state should assure the sustainability of the water resources and usual practices are the restriction/minimization of pumping in areas with critical water resources availability and during dry periods, or increase of the groundwater volumetric consumption price. Herein, a framework that can be followed in water resources management dilemmas is presented.

An alternative approach to mitigate the area's aquifer is considered, such as a water reservoir or aquifer recharge. Thus, the development cost C of the scheme is considered based on typical costs of similar works, while the annual operational AC was typically calculated equal to 1% of the development cost (Stephenson 2012). The probability ϑ_1 , water demands not to be covered is calculated statistically through a suitable probability distribution based on available hydrological data for each case study, while the cost M of transferring water from another source to support the mitigation scheme requirements e.g. local waste water treatment plant effluent for irrigation use, is also considered.

On the other hand, the probability ϑ_0 of over-pumping follows the binomial distribution (monthly monitoring of over-pumping i.e. success or failure) with a Beta prior distribution as conjugate according to the literature identified also from the optimal fit of groundwater level variations. This work proposes a scaled variation of the over-pumping cost and of environmental cost due to the lost value of groundwater. In addition, the groundwater cost GC for the area of the case study is considered, while the lost value of groundwater as a sustainable source LGV can be calculated considering its potential value as fresh potable water.

Let us consider penalty fines for K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 to increase linearly as a function of the per capita income of each country for the first, second, and third intervals of violations and that n_1 is equal to 6 and n_2 is equal to 18 successful audits. The total auditing interval is assumed equal to $N = 36$. On the other hand, the reservoir construction cost or aquifer recharge cost, C , is calculated as a function of the capacity (Fig. 2, Deliverable 3.3A). In this case study, it is assumed that the authorities perform monthly audits for over-pumping. The methodological steps to calculate the Bayesian risk and to apply the cost-benefit analysis are presented in terms of Matlab code in the Appendix.

In Bayesian risk methodology, prior information is applied by fitting the available data to the most suitable probability distribution function. Herein, the probability that over-pumping and a drought year to occur or the necessary surface water is not available is denoted as a “success” and as a “failure” and the appropriate conjugative prior distribution that matches with Binomial distribution is the beta distribution. Therefore, annual water table level variation and rainfall data are fitted to the beta distribution. The distribution’s shape parameters values α and β are validated using the mean and the variance functions of the beta distribution (Berger, 1985; Lee, 2012). The probability density function of the beta distribution, according to the calculated shape parameters, is shown in Figs. 2-9. The plots were developed to clearly identify the probability of beta-distributed values. By applying the risk function for each suggested decision using the methodology provided in detail in Deliverable 3.3A and using the provided Matlab code (see Appendix), it is obtained that the most preferable action for every site is to apply the proposed mitigation measure $A(1)$, e.g. $R(A(1)) < R(A(0))$ combining groundwater/surface water resources exploitation. The results for each case study accompanied by the relative uncertainty of estimations are presented in Table 1. The derived results are directly comparable to those produced involving data from global datasets only (deliverable 3.3A). This outcome validated the applicability of global datasets under certain circumstances of missing data providing a useful alternative.

Considering the available information and applying the proposed cost benefit analysis methodology (Eqs, 1, 2 and 3) it is obtained that for Malia case study up to 18 over-pumping violations are allowed before the mitigation measure is more affordable compare to intensive groundwater use only. On the other hand, for Arborea case study 12 violations are enough to overcome the mitigation measure cost. In Erdemli, the allowed calculated violations are equal to 16 while in Wadi El Bey, correspond to 14.

Table 1 Proposed sustainable water resources use and management in each case study

Case studies	Wadi El Bey, Tunisia	Erdemli Turkey	Arborea, Italy	Malia, Greece
Groundwater use	30%±7	34%±8	30%±2	30%±3
Surface water use	25%±4	43%±5	47%±3	55%±3
Other sources e.g. waste water treatment plant effluent	45%	23%	23%	15%
Aquifer recharge	77%±11 of groundwater use	81%±9 of groundwater use	75%±5 of groundwater use	80%±5 of groundwater use

The outcome of the examined approaches means that the decision maker should decide, based on the significance of a given issue, the data availability and quality, the public good, the environmental sustainability, and the realistic costs of each of the proposed actions. Finally, the establishment of an environmental policy in terms of penalty fines by the public authorities should consider the environmental and the public good and be dynamic in order to vary when a situation improves or worsens. This work offers a flexible decision-making tool that can be modified to address any potential hydrologic issue or decision dilemma

In the risk analysis case, where potential drought years are considered, the decision maker can obtain the optimal action based on the choice of additional water supply and the respective cost (term M) by following the methodological procedure presented with the accompanied code (Appendix). The provided code has been based on the example case assessed herein.

Fig. 2 Arborea: rainfall variations distribution function

Fig.3 Arborea: groundwater level variations (meters below surface) distribution function

Fig. 4 Erdemli: rainfall variations distribution function

Fig.5 Erdemli: groundwater level variations (meters below surface) distribution function

Fig. 6 Wadi El Bey: rainfall variations distribution function

Fig.7 Wadi El Bey: groundwater level variations (meters below surface) distribution function

Fig. 8 Malia: rainfall variations distribution function

Fig.9 Malia: groundwater level variations (meters below surface) distribution function

Conclusion

Most decision-making problems are related with a degree of uncertainty that the decision maker must address. In this work, Bayesian decision theory used the soft information provided, annual water table level variations and rainfall variations, to compare the potential losses between two possible decisions. Firstly, it combined the expected loss of a decision with the uncertain probability of paying fines due to over-pumping of an aquifer. The outcome of the latter was compared to the expected loss of a decision involving the application of a mitigation measure. The decision related to the minimum expected risk was then the most preferable. By applying Bayesian risk methodology, it was found that decision $A(1)$ (mitigation measure) provides the minimum risk.

Another decision method, under risk, was the cost-benefit approach applied to evaluate the most probable action. According to the results, the optimal action was $A(1)$ (i.e., to construct the mitigation measure). Interpreting this result with respect to the number of successful audits, the local authorities may allow up to a certain number of over-pumping violations corresponding to the first and second audit intervals.

Considering the significance of the problem from environmental and social perspectives, the quality of the available water table level variation data, as well as the optimal Bayesian decision and the calculated probability delivered by the cost-benefit approach, a long-term solution to the water resources management of the case study areas is proposed. The

proposed tool provides decision makers the ability to assess different scenarios in terms of variable loss function statements before deciding.

The next step is the potential incorporation of more input data in the proposed methodology from the living labs (stakeholders' perception), groundwater flow modelling and the decision support tool to potentially improve the results and perform a comparison analysis using different scenarios.

```

1  Appendix
2  Decision Analysis Methodology code
3
4  % Bayesian Risk Methodology
5  global a b n1 n2 N K1 K2 K3 Cost
6
7  Cost= input('give mitigation measure cost:'); %
8  a=; % Beta's function a shape parameter
9  b=; % Beta's function b shape parameter
10 n1=input('give the value of n1:'); % first interval of successful audits
11 n2= input('give the value of n2:'); % second interval of successful audits
12 N= input('give the interval of N:'); % total auditing interval
13 K1= input('give the first penalty fine:'); % penalty fines for the first interval of successful
14 audits
15 K2= input('give the second penalty fine:'); % penalty fines for the second interval of
16 successful audits
17 K3= input('give the third penalty fine:'); % penalty fines for the last interval of successful
18 audits
19
20 %The appropriate conjugate prior distribution in case of the Binomial distribution is the Beta
21 %distribution that involves the Beta function.
22 Beta_fun=beta(a,b); %beta function
23
24 %Calculation of the sums
25 % symbolic variable x denotes the probability as unknown value
26 syms x
27 SUM1=0;
28 for i=1:n1+1
29     i=i-1;
30     SUM1=SUM1+(i^2)* nchoosek(N,i)*((x^(i))*((1-x)^(N-i)));
31 end
32 SUM2=0;

```

```

33 for i=(n2+1):N
34     SUM2=SUM2+(i^2)* nchoosek(N,i)*(x^i)*((1-x)^(N-i));
35 end
36
37 % Bayesian Risk function
38 Beta_dis=(1/Beta_fun)*(x^(a-1))*((1-x)^(b-1)); % Beta distribution
39 risk=Beta_dis*K2*((N*x*(N*x-(1-x)))+(K1-K2)*SUM1+(K3-K2)*SUM2);
40
41 % Risk function of Decision A(0) by calculating the integral function (14)
42 Risk0=double(int(risk,0,1));% integration of the risk function in the interval [0,1]
43
44 % Risk function of Decision A(1)
45 % Cost of mitigation measure considering potential dry years
46 Drought= input ('weather consider potential drought or not'); % input: 0 for not drought
47 consideration, 1 otherwise
48 if Drought==0
49     Risk1=Cost;
50 else
51     M= input ('e.g. the water transport cost in €'); % Cost of water transport during dry years
52     Risk1=(Cost+M*(N/2)*8)/30; % i.e, 8/30 is the expected probability of having a year with
53 drought
54 end
55 Risk=Risk0-Risk1;
56 if (Risk>0)
57     disp ('best option is A(1)')
58 elseif (Risk==0)
59     disp ('best options is both A(0) and A(1)')
60 else
61     disp ('best option is A(0)')
62 end

```

```

63
64 % Cost Benefit analysis approach: examined case study considering potential dry years
65 clear all;
66 Y=; % The total Simulation Interval
67 Y1=; % potential dry years
68 n1=; % first interval of successful audits
69 n2=; % second interval of successful audits
70 C=; % mitigation measure cost
71 K1=; % penalty fines for the first interval of successful audits
72 K2=; % penalty fines for the second interval of successful audits
73 K3=; % penalty fines for the last interval of successful audits
74 M=input ('e.g. the water transport cost in €'); % Cost of water transport during dry years
75 for i=1:length(Y1)-1
76     sum=0;
77     for j=1:2*i
78         if (Y(j)<=n1)
79
80             sum=K1*(Y(j))^2;
81         elseif (n1<Y(j)&&(Y(j)<=n2)
82
83             sum=K1*(n1)^2+K2*(Y(j)-n1)^2;
84         else
85             sum=K1*(n1)^2+K2*(n2)^2+K3*(Y(j)-n2)^2;
86         end
87     end
88     L0(i)=(C+M*Y1(i))-sum;
89 end
90 cdfplot(L0), title ('Cumulative density probability function of ENLPV'), xlabel ('ENLPV
91 values'),ylabel('probability'), grid on

```

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